

Below are links to a variety of work I have carried out on outcomes of Indigenous hearing loss and how to mitigate these.

Dr Damien Howard

AWARENESS RAISING RESOURCES

Article that describes how hearing loss is a wedge that keeps open the gaps

<https://www.themandarin.com.au/76567-closing-the-gap-and-hearing-loss-an-invisible-barrier-obstructs-progress/>

video poster on Aboriginal kids growing up with good hearing

<https://vimeo.com/49166715>

Video poster of kids growing up with hearing loss

<https://vimeo.com/49166714>

IDENTIFYING HEARING LOSS

Game to identify hearing loss among children

http://www.eartroubles.com/blind_mans_simon_says.html

phoenix listening survey - survey to identify likely hearing loss and auditory processing problems

https://www.academia.edu/34825023/Phoenix_Listening_Survey

poster on face to face indicators on hearing loss among adults

https://www.academia.edu/36845946/Indications_of_hearing_loss_among_Indigenous_adults

EARLY CHILDHOOD AND CHILDCARE

website with resources focused on early childhood and child care

www.lookafterkidsears.com.au

Literature review on hearing loss and early childhood

https://www.academia.edu/37255373/FAFT_Hearing_Loss_Literature_Review

HEARING LOSS AND FAMILIES

Information on families on ear disease and hearing loss

https://www.academia.edu/36122406/Conductive_Hearing_Loss_and_Ear_Disease_Damien_Howard

https://www.academia.edu/37052293/First_Peoples_Child_and_Family_Review_Intercultural_Communications_and_Conductive_Hearing_Loss

families talk about ear disease and hearing loss

<https://vimeo.com/49277569>

video about family communication strategies

<https://vimeo.com/49575014>

Aboriginal adults talking about coping with hearing loss

<https://vimeo.com/49281690>

HEARING LOSS AND COMMUNICATION IN HEALTH SYSTEM

Brief discussion of communication effects of hearing loss in health system

https://www.academia.edu/37255385/Aboriginal_Health_and_Hearing_Loss_v4_2_.pdf

Hearing loss and chronic disease management

<https://healthinfonet.ecu.edu.au/healthinfonet/getContent.php?linkid=319465&title=When+talking+fails%3A+hearing+loss+and+chronic+disease>

MENTAL HEALTH AND HEARING LOSS

article on Indigenous hearing loss and mental health

https://www.academia.edu/37244570/Minced_words_the_importance_of_widespread_hearing_loss_as_an_issue_in_the_mental_health_of_Indigenous_Australians

Psycho social outcomes from ear disease

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3973984/>

THE NDIS AND HEARING LOSS

https://www.academia.edu/36759331/Improving_NDIS_access_Improving_Communications_with_Aboriginal_people_with_hearing_loss_Easy_Language_Help_from_Family_Pre_Learning_Amplification
https://www.academia.edu/36122390/Too_Much_Loud_Noise_Stories

article on conductive hearing loss leading to excessive noise exposure

https://www.academia.edu/31814101/Dangerous_Listening_The_Exposure_of_Indigenous_People_to_Excessive_Noise

[resources on excessive noise exposure in crowded Indigenous homes](https://www.academia.edu/36122390/Too_Much_Loud_Noise_Stories)
https://www.academia.edu/36122390/Too_Much_Loud_Noise_Stories

EDUCATION

Article on Indigenous students hearing loss

<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1069625.pdf>

Video on CHL and school behaviour problems

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vZP0z3Hrcno>

Aboriginal teacher talking about her experiences as a child with hearing loss.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gDADG6kyjug>

Article on how teachers can refer wrong kids for hearing tests because of cultural differences in attentional styles

https://www.academia.edu/37249183/Classroom_Case_Study_Cross_Cultural_Obstacles_to_the_Referral_of_Aboriginal_Children_for_Hearing_Tests

Doctoral thesis on learning and behavioural problems of Indigenous students with Conductive Hearing Loss

https://espace.cdu.edu.au/eserv/cdu:6524/Thesis_CDU_6524_Howard_D.pdf

HEARING LOSS AND INVOLVEMENT IN THE CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM

Article describing that 94% of Aboriginal inmates in the NT were found to have a hearing loss

https://www.academia.edu/37255353/Massive_Prevalence_of_Hearing_Loss_Among_Aboriginal_Inmates_in_the_NT

Article discussing hearing loss and criminal justice system

https://www.academia.edu/37255351/Aboriginal_Hearing_Loss_and_the_Criminal_justice_system

Submission on hearing loss and criminal justice

https://www.academia.edu/31713784/Submission_to_criminal_justice_sub_087.pdf

Web presentation on ear disease and involvement in criminal justice system

<https://www.deafeducation.vic.edu.au/Professional-Learning/Pages/ConductHLoss.aspx>

INDIGENOUS HEARING LOSS, EMPLOYMENT AND ORGANISATIONAL FUNCTIONING

Chapter 6 from Listening Learning and Work on how hearing loss among staff affects organisational functioning and how hearing loss among governing boards affects governance

https://www.academia.edu/37255331/CHAPTER_SIX_ears_and_organisations

Book on cross cultural management including sections on hearing loss

https://www.academia.edu/37052304/Mixed_Messages

Presentation on governance and hearing loss

https://www.academia.edu/31713794/Communication_Listening_and_Governance_Communication

Submission on hearing loss employment and training

https://www.academia.edu/31713785/Training_and_employment_outcomes_for_Indigenous_adults_with_conductive_hearing_loss_Submission_to_the_NCVER_on_future_research_priorities

Book on Indigenous hearing loss and employment

<https://www.amazon.com.au/Supporting-employees-have-hearing-loss-ebook/dp/B00Y9XDR22>

VIDEO Indigenous people talking about hearing loss at work

<https://vimeo.com/49166716>

VIDEO RESOURCES

other resources

<https://independent.academia.edu/howarddamien>